

Once upon a time...the Generation Swipe: the impact of algorithm-governed social media on youth socialization, online bullying and school education

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Author: [Giorgia Scuderi](#)

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Abstract:

The aim of this paper is to share some of the key findings of an ethnographic study on youth online socialization dynamics: the difficulties of school systems and policies in keeping up with the technological and societal changes, alongside a deepening intergenerational gap. According to my analysis, such challenges often stem from a limited adult´s digital literacy and struggle to respond to the influence of material forces in young people's lives.

Bringing in the conceptualization of subjectification from Butler (1990) and Davies (2000, 2006), and meaning making from Barad (2007), I investigated the role of social media in the making of youth´s beliefs and values, negotiation of social norms, and their enforcement through online bullying.

The ethnographic study engaged with young people aged 11 to 15 years old, along with their families and educators from diverse contexts, in Italy and Denmark. Using creative methodological approaches such as storytelling workshops, backed by interviews and observation, the study collected in depth insights on the complex youth´s social dimension. The schools and families in my research material find themselves challenged by new sources of education: online platforms. The current generation of young people - by some termed "Generation Swipe" - is born into a reality where technology affect their socialization and educational systems. Accustomed to swiping away anything deemed boring, my analysis shows that most of the teenagers find refuge in their devices. This behavior can be attributed to a school that may not fully engage them and a family education far from the values and norms they absorb online, that become part of their performed identity. My analysis reveals that their devices, with social media, instant messaging and online gaming platforms, are considered safe environments, carefully tailored to their preferences. But they are also seen as non-human affects able to teach them, offer comfort and understanding. However, they contribute to the emergence of new forms of marginalization difficult to address.

"For me, the phone is everything.

It's my companion, sometimes it's my mother because it tells me what to do. It's a teacher. [...] It helps me remember what to do, and it tells me 'go brush your teeth' or at what time I need to do my homework."

Laura, 11 years old

The findings open a reflection on the need for practice and policy-oriented education research, to support school communities and foster collaboration between families and educators, without neglecting children's voices.

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